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Mutu I Hemin Dosage Timecourse Cell viability

Fig S1. Hemin dose titration and cell viability. To determine the relationship between hemin dosage and cell viability, Mutu I cells were untreated or treated with hemin at concentrations of 62.5, 125, 250 and 500 μ M and cell viability was measured every 24 hours for 4 days. The lowest concentration of 62.5 had the highest viability.

Fig S2. TPA/NaBu treatment of Mutu I cells as a positive control. (A) BZLF1 and BRLF1 transcripts measured in TPA/NaBu-treated Mutu I cells by RT-qPCR. **(B)** Gating strategy for CD138/gp350 staining experiments on Mutu I cells treated with TPA/NaBu. **(C)** Dual positive CD138/gp350 populations 48 hours post TPA/NaBu treatment.

Fig S3: Comparison of viability post hemin treatment between Ramos and Mutu I. Time course of EBV- negative Ramos (A) cell viability post hemin treatment and EBV positive Mutu I (B) cell viability post hemin treatment.

A Mutu I

B Ramos

Fig S4: Gating strategy for Mutu I and Ramos flow cytometry analyses. Mutu I (A) and Ramos (B) BL cell lines were analyzed in FlowJo by gating in the order of lymphocytes, single cells, then live dead.

Cycloheximide alone

Cycloheximide + hemin

Fig S5: BACH2 stability using cycloheximide. Stability of BACH2 was measured using cycloheximide (CHX) alone (A) and quantified (B) and in combination with hemin (C) and quantified (D). N=3 for all western blots.

Fig S6: BACH2 sequencing. (A) Schematic of the BACH2 gene, corresponding mRNA with exons shown in yellow, and the resulting transcriptional regulator protein shown in tan. Dotted lines represent primers used to capture exons that encode for the transcriptional regulator. (B) Schematic of the BACH2 transcriptional regulator with prominent features in green (BTB domain, bZIP- basic leucine zipper, CLS-cytoplasmic localization signal) and the five cysteine-proline motifs that serve as heme binding sites shown in red, labeled with their amino acid positions. (C) PCR products from exons 4 through 8 for each cell line were run on a DNA agarose gel.

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BACH2_Mutu	MSVDEKPDSPMYVYESTVHCTNILLGLNDQRKDKILCDVTLIVERKEFRAHRAVLAACSE	60
BACH2_Ramos	MSVDEKPDSPMYVYESTVHCTNILLGLNDQRKDKILCDVTLIVERKEFRAHRAVLAACSE	60
BACH2_BL41	MSVDEKPDSPMYVYESTVHCTNILLGLNDQRKDKILCDVTLIVERKEFRAHRAVLAACSE	60
BACH2_BL8	MSVDEKPDSPMYVYESTVHCTNILLGLNDQRKDKILCDVTLIVERKEFRAHRAVLAACSE	60
BACH2_REF	MSVDEKPDSPMYVYESTVHCTNILLGLNDQRKDKILCDVTLIVERKEFRAHRAVLAACSE	60

BACH2_Mutu	YFWQALVGQTKNDLVVSLPEE - TARGFGPLLQFAYTAKLLLSRENIREVIRCAEFLRMHN	119
BACH2_Ramos	YFWQALVGQTKNDLVVSLPEE - TARGFGPLLQFAYTAKLLLSRENIREVIRCAEFLRMHN	119
BACH2_BL41	YFWQALVGQTKNDLVVSLPEE - TARGFGPLLQFAYTAKLLLSRENIREVIRCAEFLRMHN	119
BACH2_BL8	YFWQALVGQTKNDLVVSLPEE - TARGFGPLLQFAYTAKLLLSRENIREVIRCAEFLRMHN	119
BACH2_REF	YFWQALVGQTKNDLVVSLPEE TARGFGPLLQFAYTAKLLLSRENIREVIRCAEFLRMHN	120

BACH2_Mutu	LEDSCFSFLQTQLLNSEDLFVCRKDAACQRPHeDcensageeEdeeeetmdsETAKMAC	179
BACH2_Ramos	LEDSCFSFLQTQLLNSEDLFVCRKDAACQRPHeDcensageeEdeeeetmdseTAKMAC	179
BACH2_BL41	LEDSCFSFLQTQLLNSEDLFVCRKDAACQRPHeDcensageeEdeeeetmdseTAKMAC	179
BACH2_BL8	LEDSCFSFLQTQLLNSEDLFVCRKDAACQRPHeDcensageeEdeeeetmdseTAKMAC	179
BACH2_REF	LEDSCFSFLQTQLLNSEDLFVCRKDAACQRPHEDCENSAGEEEDDEEETMDSETAKMAC	180

BACH2_Mutu	PRDQMLPEPISF EAAAI PVAEKEEALLPEPDPVTDTKESSEKDAL TQYPRYKQYLACTK	239
BACH2_Ramos	PRDQMLPEPISF EAAAI PVAEKEEALLPEPDPVTDTKESSEKDAL TQYPRYKQYLACTK	239
BACH2_BL41	PRDQMLPEPISF EAAAI PVAEKEEALLPEPDPVTDTKESSEKDAL TQYPRYKQYLACTK	239
BACH2_BL8	PRDQMLPEPISF EAAAI PVAEKEEALLPEPDPVTDTKESSEKDAL TQYPRYKQYLACTK	239
BACH2_REF	PRDQMLPEPISF EAAAI PVAEKEEALLPEPDPVTDTKESSEKDAL TQYPRYKQYLACTK	240

BACH2_Mutu	NVYNASSHSTSGFASTFR EDNSSNLSKPLARGQIKseppseeneesITLCLSGDEPDA	299
BACH2_Ramos	NVYNASSHSTSGFASTFR EDNSSNLSKPLARGQIKseppseeneesITLCLSGDEPDA	299
BACH2_BL41	NVYNASSHSTSGFASTFR EDNSSNLSKPLARGQIKseppseeneesITLCLSGDEPDA	299
BACH2_BL8	NVYNASSHSTSGFASTFR EDNSSNLSKPLARGQIKseppseeneesITLCLSGDEPDA	299
BACH2_REF	NVYNASSHSTSGFASTFR EDNSSNLSKPLARGQIKSEPPSEENEESITLCLSGDEPDA	300

BACH2_Mutu	KDRAGDVMDRKQpspaptptapagaACLEERSR SVASPSCL-----	340
BACH2_Ramos	KDRAGDVMDRKQpspaptptapagaaCLERSR-----	332
BACH2_BL41	KDRAGDVMDRKQpspaptptapagaaCLERSRAWPRPPA*VSVQHNEKCALFSITKSVE	358
BACH2_BL8	KDRAGDVMDRKQpspaptptapagaaCLERSR SVASPSCL-----RSLFSITKSVE	351
BACH2_REF	KDRAGDVMDRKQPSAPTPTAPAGAACLEERSR SVASPSCL-----RSLFSITKSVE	352

BACH2_Mutu	---PSTSQQHFARSPACPFDKGITQGD LKTDYTPFTGNYGQPHVGGKEVSNFTMGSP LR	396
BACH2_Ramos	---PSTSQQHFARSPACPFDKGITQGD IKT DYTPFTGNYGQPHVGGKEVSNFTMGSP LR	370
BACH2_BL41	LSGLPSTSQQHFARSPACPFDKGITQGD LKTDYTPFTGNYGQPHVGGKEVSNFTMGSP LR	418
BACH2_BL8	LSGLPSTSQQHFARSPACPFDKGITQGD LKTDYTPFTGNYGQPHVGGKEVSNFTMGSP LR	411
BACH2_REF	LSGLPSTSQQHFARSPACPFDKGITQGD LKTDYTPFTGNYGQPHVGGKEVSNFTMGSP LR	412

BACH2_Mutu	GPGLEALCKQEGELDRRSVIFSSSACDQvstsvhsysgvsSLDKDLSEVPVKGLWVGAGQ	456
BACH2_Ramos	GPGLEALCKQEGELDRRSVIFSSSACDQvstsvhsysgvsSLDKDLSEVPVKGLWVGAGQ	430
BACH2_BL41	GPGLEALCKQEGELDRRSVIFSSSACDQvstsvhsysgvsSLDKDLSEVPVKGLWVGAGQ	478
BACH2_BL8	GPGLEALCKQEGELDRRSVIFSSSACDQvstsvhsysgvsSLDKDLSEVPVKGLWVGAGQ	471
BACH2_REF	GPGLEALCKQEGELDRRSVIFSSSACDQVSTSVHSYSGVSSLDKDLSEVPVKGLWVGAGQ	472

BACH2_Mutu	SLPSSQAYSHGGLMADHLPGRMRPNTSCPVPIKVCPRSPPLEtrtrtssscssysYAEDG	516
BACH2_Ramos	SLPSSQAYSHGGLMADHLPGRMRPNTSCPVPIKVCPRSPPLEtrtrtssscssysYAEDG	490
BACH2_BL41	SLPSSQAYSHGGLMADHLPGRMRPNTSCPVPIKVCPRSPPLEtrtrtssscssysYAEDG	538
BACH2_BL8	SLPSSQAYSHGGLMADHLPGRMRPNTSCPVPIKVCPRSPPLEtrtrtssscssysYAEDG	531
BACH2_REF	SLPSSQAYSHGGLMADHLPGRMRPNTSCPVPIKVCPRSPPLETRTRTSSSCSSYSYAEDG	532

BACH2_Mutu	SGGSPCSLPLCEFSSSPCSQGARFLATEHQEPGLMGDMYQVRPQIKCEQSYGTNSSDE	576
BACH2_Ramos	SGGSPCSLPLCEFSSSPCSQGARFLATEHQEPGLMGDMYQVRPQIKCEQSYGTNSSDE	550
BACH2_BL41	SGGSPCSLPLCEFSSSPCSQGARFLATEHQEPGLMGDMYQVRPQIKCEQSYGTNSSDE	598
BACH2_BL8	SGGSPCSLPLCEFSSSPCSQGARFLATEHQEPGLMGDMYQVRPQIKCEQSYGTNSSDE	591
BACH2_REF	SGGSPCSLPLCEFSSSPCSQGARFLATEHQEPGLMGDMYQVRPQIKCEQSYGTNSSDE	592

BACH2_Mutu	SGSFEADSESCPVDQRGQEV-----IKMKHLTSEQLEFIH DV	614
BACH2_Ramos	SGSFEADSESCPVDQRGQELTLKLPFPVDQITDLPRNDFQMMIKMKHLTSEQLEFIH DV	610
BACH2_BL41	SGSFEADSESCPVDQRGHEV--KLFPFPVDQITDLPRNDFQMMIKMKHLTSEQLEFIH DV	656
BACH2_BL8	SGSFEADSESCPVDQRGHEV--KLFPFPVDQITDLPRNDFQMMIKMKHLTSEQLEFIH DV	649
BACH2_REF	SGSFEADSESCPVDQRGQEV--KLFPFPVDQITDLPRNDFQMMIKMKHLTSEQLEFIH DV	650

BACH2_Mutu	RRRSKNRIAAQRCKRKRKLDICIQLNLECEIRKLVFPVDQITDLPRNDFQMMIKMKEKELLS	674
BACH2_Ramos	RRRSKNRIAAQRCKRKRKLDICIQLNLECEIRGE-----NVCEKELLS	651
BACH2_BL41	RRRSKNRIAAQRCKRKRKLDICIQLNLECEI-----RCEKELLS	693
BACH2_BL8	RRRSKNRIAAQRCKRKRKLDICIQLNLECEIR-----VCEKELLS	687
BACH2_REF	RRRSKNRIAAQRCKRKRKLDICIQLNLECEIRK-----LVCEKELLS	690

BACH2_Mutu	ERNQLKACMGELLDNF SCLSQEVCRDIQSPEIQALHRYCPVLRPMDLPTASSINPAPLG	734
BACH2_Ramos	ERNQLKACMGELLDNF SCLSQEVCRDIQSPEIQALHRYCPVLRPMDLPTASSINPAPLG	711
BACH2_BL41	ERNQLKACMGELLDNF SCLSQEVCRDIQSPEIQALHRYCPVLRPMDLPTASSINPAPLG	753
BACH2_BL8	ERNQLKACMGELLDNF SCLSQEVCRDIQSPEIQALHRYCPVLRPMDLPTASSINPAPLG	747
BACH2_REF	ERNQLKACMGELLDNF SCLSQEVCRDIQSPEIQALHRYCPVLRPMDLPTASSINPAPLG	750

BACH2_Mutu	AEQNI AASQCAVGENVPCCLEPGAAPP GPPWAPSN TSENCTSGRRLEGTDPGTF SERGPP	794
BACH2_Ramos	AEQNI AASQCAVGENVPCCLEPGAAPP GPPWAPSN TSENCTSGRRLEGTDPGTF SERGPP	771
BACH2_BL41	AEQNI AASQCAVGENVPCCLEPGAAPP GPPWAPSN TSENCTSGRRLEGTDPGTF SERGPP	813
BACH2_BL8	AEQNI AASQCAVGENVPCCLEPGAAPP GPPWAPSN TSENCTSGRRLEGTDPGTF SERGPP	807
BACH2_REF	AEQNI AASQCAVGENVPCCLEPGAAPP GPPWAPSN TSENCTSGRRLEGTDPGTF SERGPP	810

BACH2_Mutu	LEPRSQT VTFDQCQEMTDKCTTDEQPRKDYT	825
BACH2_Ramos	LEPRSQT VTFDQCQEMTDKCTTDEQPRKDYT	802
BACH2_BL41	LEPRSQT VTFDQCQEMTDKCTTDEQPRKDYT	844
BACH2_BL8	LEPRSQT VTFDQCQEMTDKCTTDEQPRKDYT	838
BACH2_REF	LEPRSQT VTFDQCQEMTDKCTTDEQPRKDYT	841

Fig S7: BACH2 transcriptional regulator sequences from BL cell lines. BACH2 transcriptional regulator sequences derived from Mutu I, Ramos, BL41, and BL8 and compared to the NCBI BACH2 reference sequence. Cysteine proline motifs that serve as heme binding sites are highlighted in yellow.

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Fig S8: Gating strategy for BACH2 siRNA experiments. (A) BACH2 siRNA or scramble cells were gated on lymphocytes, single cells, live cells, then transfected cells. (B) CD138 expression compared between scramble and BACH2 siRNA.